

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS: ITS IMPACT ON KNOWLEDGE, PRACTICE AND EFFICACY OF TEACHERS AND PUPILS' LEARNING OUTCOMES

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Professional Development Programs: Its Impact on Knowledge, Practice and Efficacy of Teachers and Pupils' Learning Outcomes

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Abstract

The study attempted to present the professional development programs and its implication to knowledge, practice, and efficacy of teachers and pupils' learning outcomes. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized and the Statistical tools used in the study were mean, standard deviation, frequency count, and percentages to analyze the extent of the professional development program, the level of pupils' learning outcomes. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the level of pupils; learning outcomes and the extent of teachers' professional development program. Findings revealed that professional development program had a high impact to teachers' knowledge and teachers' practice but it has a very high impact on teachers' efficacy. Additionally, there more pupils who had "satisfactory" learning outcomes. It was also found out in the statistical treatment of data that teachers' knowledge, practice, and efficacy do not significantly correlate to pupils' learning outcomes. As a summary, pupils' learning outcomes was influenced by factors other than the teachers' professional development. Subsequently, it was recommended to the higher school authorities in the department to design and craft a comprehensive approach of professional development program that is inclusive to the specific learning needs of the public school learners.

Keywords: *professional development program, pupils' learning outcomes, teachers' knowledge, teachers' practice, teachers' efficacy*

Introduction

Teachers' professional development through occupational trainings and graduate education program is recognized as a significant component of school leadership which helps intensify and address the issues on ineffectual teaching and learning in the Philippine classrooms.

The study on teachers' professional development is anchored on DM 50, s. 2020 on the professional development priorities for teachers and school heads which shall support the realization of DepEd's goal of continuous upskilling and reskilling of teachers and school leaders that will result in better learning outcomes.

The Department of Education is presently active in implementing the fundamental reforms that includes efforts for human resource development at all levels to support quality performance of schools and learners. The Department's package of policy reforms known as the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) seeks "to systematically improve critical regulatory, institutional, structural, financial, cultural, physical and informational conditions affecting basic education provision, access and delivery on the ground. These policy reforms are expected to create critical changes necessary to further accelerate, broaden, deepen and sustain the improved education effort already being started" (BESRA PIP, 2006).

Professional development programs help increase and improve teachers' teaching effectiveness which impact to learners and the school. The training identifies features of effective professional learning and provide teachers with variety of techniques for effective classroom practice to improve pupils' learning outcomes.

Gonzales (2021) pointed out that teachers' professional development programs stimulate teachers to enhance and improve teaching effectiveness which impact pupils' learning outcomes. It was also emphasized that professional development trainings for teachers help intensify teaching knowledge, provide an opportunity to improve classroom practice, and more likely to lead to significant and sustained improvement in pupils' learning performance and academic achievements.

Teaching needs for sophisticated methods and strategies to meet pupils' learning and development needs through the school-based continuous professional development program or the learning action cell, graduate education, and special trainings from Southeast Asian Ministry of Education Organization or SEAMEO for Guro21 and the like which help capacitate teachers to improve teaching.

Additionally, Bernal and Wilson (2020) purported that teachers' professional development programs in the Department of Education were done through the use of a combination of professional development strategies such as workshops, accredited courses, online learning, mentoring and action learning. Further, it was emphasized that teachers' professional development programs are mediating strategies that help improve teachers' knowledge, classroom practice, and pupils' learning and efficacy.

The most effective professional development programs will engage teams of teachers to emphasize on improving teaching by focusing and converging on the learning needs of pupils and allow themselves to learn techniques and tested-strategies to ensure that all learners will achieve success.

Further, it was highlighted that professional development programs for teachers included the contextual and structural features of the programs such as school support, context, and participation as well as the mediating factors which include the level of commitment to personal and professional development in the teaching profession and the development outcomes which can be measured through knowledge, practice, and pupils' learning and efficacy (Valdez and Hawley, 2021).

Consequently, Carpentero (2021) ascertained that teachers' professional development is negligibly correlated to teachers' teaching effective practice, knowledge, and pupils' learning outcomes and efficacy, hence, the researcher is motivated to conduct this investigation to find out if there is no significant relationship between professional development programs to teachers' effectiveness and pupils' learning outcomes.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the impact of professional development program to teachers' knowledge, practice and efficacy and pupils' learning outcomes. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the impact of professional development programs of teachers in terms of the following;
 - 1.1. teachers' knowledge;
 - 1.2. teacher's practice; and,
 - 1.3. teaching efficacy?
2. What is the level of pupils' learning outcomes when they are categorized as;
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory; and,
 - 2.5. did not meet expectations?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the professional development program of teachers and pupils' learning outcomes?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of survey questionnaires, interview, and focused-group discussion (FGD) .

Respondents

The respondents of the study are the twenty (20) teachers of Baluarte Elementary School (9 teachers with 90 pupils) and Pagalungan Elem School (11 teachers with 110 pupils), Cagayan de Oro City. There were twenty (20) teacher-respondents of the study who answered the survey questionnaire on teachers' professional development program and two hundred (200) pupils where their learning outcomes be inter played to the independent variable. The respondents were chosen purposely because of their number and for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The survey instrument is composed of four (4) major components. The first component is on teachers' teaching knowledge with twenty (20) indicators. The second component is on teachers' teaching practice with twenty (20) indicators while the third component is on teachers' teaching efficacy with twenty (20) indicators. Further, the fourth component is on pupils' learning outcomes which measured pupils' academic performance for the given academic year which are categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro. The same permission was asked by the researcher to the teacher-respondents to participate in the study and to the parents of pupils-respondents to allow the researcher utilize their child's learning outcomes as the variable of this study. Moreover, the parents were assured that the data gathered were treated to its highest

confidentiality and be used for research purposes only.

After the respondents provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated, and submitted for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment are utilized to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of professional development program in terms of teachers' knowledge, practice, and efficacy.

For Problem 2, frequency and percentages were used to present the pupils' learning outcomes.

For Problem 3, Pearson r was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between teachers' professional development program and pupils' learning outcomes.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on professional development programs its implication on knowledge, practice and efficacy of teachers and pupils' learning outcomes. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the problem presented.

Problem 1. What is the impact of professional development programs of teachers in terms of the following; Teachers' knowledge, Teacher's practice, and Teaching efficacy?

Professional development programs help increase and improve teachers' teaching effectiveness which impact to learners and the school. The training identifies features of effective professional learning and provide teachers with variety of techniques for effective classroom practice to improve pupils' learning outcomes.

Table 1.1 shows the mean distribution of the extent of the impact of professional development programs of teachers in terms of teachers' knowledge.

Table 1.1. Mean Distribution of the Impact of Professional Development of Teachers in terms of Teachers' Knowledge

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Gain knowledge on different teaching strategies after the development program	4.40	.820	Very High Impact
2. Gain knowledge in utilizing teaching methods inclusive to the pupils' learning needs	3.80	1.361	High Impact
3. Gain knowledge in dealing with the content teach	4.10	.718	High Impact
4. Gain knowledge on developing self-confidence in teaching	4.10	.718	High Impact
5. Gain knowledge in dealing with diverse learners	4.00	.648	High Impact
6. Gain knowledge in assessing pupils' learning.	3.90	.552	High Impact
7. Gain knowledge in evaluating pupils' mastery learning	3.70	.470	High Impact
8. Gain knowledge in developing pupils' learning focus.	3.60	.680	High Impact
9. Gain knowledge in dealing with pupils with problems.	3.60	.680	High Impact
10. Gain knowledge in dealing with the learning issues of pupils.	3.50	.827	High Impact
11. Gain knowledge in dealing with individual differences	3.20	1.196	Moderate
12. Gain knowledge in motivating pupils to engage in class.	3.00	1.297	Moderate
13. Gain knowledge in responding pupil's misbehavior	2.90	1.410	Moderate
14. Gain knowledge in dealing with psycho-social issues	2.80	1.436	Moderate
15. Gain knowledge in dealing with interruptions.	3.20	1.196	Moderate
16. Gain knowledge in intensified classroom management	3.00	1.297	Moderate
17. Gain knowledge in dealing with interpersonal conflict	2.90	1.410	Moderate
18. Gain knowledge in dealing with school issues	2.80	1.436	Moderate
19. Gain knowledge in dealing with organization conflict	2.90	1.410	Moderate
20. Gain knowledge in dealing with multifarious school functions and ancillary assignments	2.80	1.436	Moderate
Overall Mean	3.41	1.049	High Impact

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Impact/3.41-4.20 High Impact/2.61-3.40 Moderate Impact/1.81-2.60 Low Impact/1.00-1.80 No Impact

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of the impact of professional development of teachers in terms of teachers' knowledge. Overall, it was found out that professional development of teachers has "High Impact" to teachers' knowledge with a mean of 3.41 (SD=1.049). This result indicates that teachers' knowledge is based on teachers' teaching awareness which can be attributed to the influence of professional development and training programs.

Bell and Goe (2020) asserted that effective teacher is not only someone who discovers the opportunities for conveying the best out of their subjects but also holds academic coordination and achieves their classroom goals by accentuating academic instructions.

The indicator "Gain knowledge on different teaching strategies after the development program" obtained the highest mean value of 4.40 (SD=.820) which is verbally described as "Very High Impact" which implies that development programs through trainings,

seminars, and conferences provide technical expertise and enhance work efficiency and effectiveness to teachers. Thus, it is imperative the professional development for teachers should be provided continuously to the school administration.

This finding was supported by Stringer and Irwing (2022) averred that teaching knowledge, teaching effectiveness and proficiency are demonstrated through teachers' training and development program. Teaching performance is also measured in terms of utilization of varied teaching approaches in different learning areas in order for pupils to fully engaged in learning activities.

Further, it was exemplified that teachers' teaching knowledge is associated with teaching performance effectiveness contribute in the education process by performing a wide range of responsibilities such as managing curriculum, maintaining relationship with parents and colleagues. Additionally, effective teacher holds the most prominent and highest place in an education system and the effectiveness of instruction depends on the quality of dispositions the teacher possesses.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.80 (SD= 1.436) which is verbally described as "Moderate Impact" in the indicators "Gain knowledge in dealing with school issues" and "Gain knowledge in dealing with multifarious school functions and ancillary assignments". The results indicate that there is a reasonable impact on teachers' knowledge in dealing with school issues and in dealing with different school functions and auxiliary or supplemental assignments.

Gupta and Verma (2020) pointed out that teachers learn from dealing with different school issues and challenges as well as performing different school functions and committee works and chairmanships in academic and non-academic school committees and activities. The different school issues and ancillary work assignments help gain perspectives and strengthen teachers' knowledge.

Table 1.2. Mean Distribution of the Impact of Professional Development of Teachers in terms of Teachers' Practice

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Makes clearer links between teaching goals and classroom activities.	4.40	.940	Very High
2. Manages classroom structure and activities more effectively.	4.40	.940	Very High
3. Uses effective teaching and learning strategies.	4.40	.940	Very High
4. Selects appropriate learning activities of the learning content.	4.30	.923	Very High
5. Uses more appropriate teaching strategies based on pupils' learning needs.	4.20	.894	High
6. Utilizes teaching strategies appropriate to classroom context.	4.20	.894	High
7. Utilizes teaching strategies that are challenging and engaging.	4.10	.767	High
8. Utilizes teaching strategies that develops independent learning.	4.10	.718	High
9. Better able to meet individual learning needs of pupils.	4.10	.718	High
10. Links assessment into teaching and learning cycle effectively.	4.00	.648	High
11. Provides feedback on pupils' learning performance to parents.	3.90	.552	High
12. Designs mechanism to engage parents in learning development of the child.	3.90	.552	High
13. Designs learning materials based on the inclusive learning needs of pupils	3.80	.615	High
14. Designs effective feedback mechanism to assist and support learning improvement	3.80	.615	High
15. Provides regular follow-up on pupils' learning performance	3.80	.615	High
16. Empowers parents in teaching and learning activities in school	3.60	1.046	High
17. Forges collaboration among fellow teachers to help pupils in need.	3.90	.718	High
18. Provides simple, easy-to-understand, inspiring and engaging learning activities	3.90	.718	High
19. Provides experiential learning activities where every pupil is stimulated to engage	3.80	.894	High
20. Provides activities that engage pupils in higher order thinking	3.80	.894	High
Overall Mean	3.82	.780	High Impact

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Impact/3.41-4.20 High Impact/2.61-3.40 Moderate Impact/1.81-2.60 Low Impact/1.00-1.80 No Impact

Table 1.2 displays the mean distribution of the impact of professional development of teachers in terms of teachers' practice. Overall, it was revealed that professional development of teachers has "High Impact" to teachers' practice with a mean of 3.82 (SD=.780). This result indicates that teachers' practice provides an opportunity for teachers to grow their knowledge and sharpen their skills, which can lead to better student outcomes. It is a way for teachers to collaborate with their colleagues.

Guskey (2020) averred that effective teachers' teaching practice provides opportunities to pupils to improve learning engagements and academic outcomes. It was also emphasized that effective teaching practice allows pupils to engage and enjoy learning because teachers can express the passion for their work and inspire them to take an active class participation.

The indicators "Makes clearer links between teaching goals and classroom activities"; "Manages classroom structure and activities more effectively" and "Uses effective teaching and learning strategies" obtained the highest mean value of 4.40 (SD=.940) which is verbally described as "Very High Impact" which imply that professional development of teachers has improved teachers' practice through a stronger and vibrant links between teaching goals and classroom activities. It also helps teachers improve classroom structure and intensify the utilization of functional and pupil-centered teaching approaches and learning strategies.

This finding was supported by Gupta and Verma (2020) who found out that effective teaching practice is influenced by teachers' knowledge, strategies, processes and behaviors which will allow them to inspire learners to achieve and perform in the class. Effective teachers' teaching practice stimulate pupils to use their intellect and energy to improve learning and achieve the desired outcomes.

In a similar investigation, Pajares (2021) espoused that the best teachers' practice to become more effective in teaching is to be always

prepared in the class, set clear and fair expectations from the learners, possess positive attitude towards the learners and their ability to learn, patient with learners' inadequacies, and assess their teaching on a regular basis. Additionally, it was pointed out that teachers should be able to adjust their teaching strategies to fit both the learners and the materials, recognizing the learning gaps and pupils' learning capabilities.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 3.60 (SD= 1.046) which is verbally described as "High Impact" in the indicator "Empowers parents in teaching and learning activities in school". The result indicates that parents were empowered to provide needed learning activities in order to enhance pupils' learning. Thus, it is imperative to stimulate parents to provide the necessary learning activities at home to complement learning.

Pajares (2021) averred that teachers' practice of empowering parents to provide the needed learning opportunities to their children at home complements the learning experiences of children in school. Teachers also need to empower parents to take the responsibility of teaching their children not just to enhance literacy and numeracy but also the desirable and positive attitude, good behavior, and above all the attributes for good citizenship.

Table 1.3. Mean Distribution of the Impact of Professional Development of Teachers in terms of Teachers' Efficacy

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Provides activities that meet the learning needs of pupils	4.40	.940	Very High
2. Provides learning activities that develop pupils' social and emotional skills	4.40	.940	Very High
3. Provides learning activities that develop pupils' physical and mental stability	4.40	.940	Very High
4. Provides learning activities that develop pupils' critical and creative thinking	4.30	.923	Very High
5. Provides learning activities that develop pupils' communication skills	4.20	.894	High
6. Provides learning activities that develop pupils' appreciation skills.	4.20	.894	High
7. Provides learning activities that develop pupils' consciousness on global and environmental issues	4.10	.767	High
8. Provides learning activities that develop pupils' good citizenship skills.	4.30	.718	Very High
9. Provides learning activities that promote nationalism, patriotism	4.40	.801	Very High
10. Provides learning activities that promote pupils' initiative, innovativeness, and resourcefulness	4.30	.680	Very High
11. Provides learning activities that promote pupils' resilience and flexibility	4.30	.656	Very High
12. Provides learning activities that promote pupils' sense of ownership and community	4.30	.656	Very High
13. Provides learning activities that promote pupils' confidence and self-worth.	4.40	.680	Very High
14. Provides learning performance that promote collaboration and cooperation	4.30	.656	Very High
15. Provides learning performance that promote the sense of responsibility and accountability	4.30	.656	Very High
16. Provides learning performance that promote pupils'	4.10	.718	High
17. Provides learning performance that stimulates engagements to pupils-at-risk	4.10	.718	High
18. Provides learning performance that are based on local and context situations	4.10	.718	High
19. Provides learning performance that stimulates pupils with special needs	4.10	.718	High
20. Provides learning performance that enhance pupils' cognitive skills	4.10	.718	High
Overall Mean	4.25	.769	Very High Impact

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Impact/3.41-4.20 High Impact/2.61-3.40 Moderate Impact/1.81-2.60 Low Impact/1.00-1.80 No Impact

Table 1.3 displays the mean distribution of the impact of professional development of teachers in terms of teachers' efficacy. Overall, it was revealed that professional development of teachers has "Very High Impact" to teachers' efficacy with a mean of 4.25 (SD=.769). This result indicates that teachers' professional development program greatly contributed to teachers' teaching efficiency and effectiveness which means that the development program helps the teachers with not only adding new skill sets to their resumes but also learning new teaching tools and techniques and building professional relationships. The development program helps educators in connecting their subject material to the newly learned skills and use these skills to optimise learning.

Gonzales (2021) exemplified that teachers' efficacy is measured in the way they help learners and pupils learn, their ability to bring effectively the program to pupils, and their willingness to provide the learning inclusive learning environment to students with special learning needs.

The indicators "Provides activities that meet the learning needs of pupils", "Provides learning activities that develop pupils' social and emotional skills", and, "Provides learning activities that develop pupils' physical and mental stability" obtained the highest mean value of 4.40 (SD=.940) which is verbally described as "Very High Impact". This means that teachers' professional development greatly impacts teachers to provide activities that meet the learning needs of pupils and learning activities that develop pupils' social and emotional skills.

Carpentero (2021) averred that teacher efficacy is the teachers' ability to influence and make learning more interesting and engaging to learners even to those who have special needs, those with learning difficulties, and those who are unmotivated because of some personal and social issues.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.10 (SD= .718) which is verbally described as "High Impact" in the indicators "Provides learning activities that develop pupils' consciousness on global and environmental issues"; "provides learning performance that promote pupils' learning performance"; "Provides learning performance that stimulates engagements to pupils-at-risk"; " Provides learning performance that are based on local and context situations"; "Provides learning performance that stimulates pupils with special need"

and, “Provides learning performance that enhance pupils’ cognitive skills”. These results indicate that teachers’ professional development program greatly influence teachers’ efficacy in providing learning opportunities for pupils where they can experience a stimulating learning environment. It can also be deduced that teachers’ professional development training program will help develop teachers address the learning issues among struggling and academically-challenged learners.

Cheng, et al (2020) stated that deliberately employing acts of teaching to improve individuals who are struggling academically is addressed through teachers’ efficacy or effectiveness. It was suggested that skills and emotions are intertwined and therefore some of the stress that fosters negative attitudes is reduced when individuals are provided with adequate instruction as the manifestations of teaching efficacy.

Problem 2. What is the level of pupils’ learning outcomes when they are categorized as; Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectations?

Pupils’ learning outcomes are statements that specify pupils will know, be able to do or be able to demonstrate when they have completed or participated and satisfactory completed in a course or program. Table 2 presents the level of pupils’ learning outcomes when they are categorized as Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectations.

Table 2. *Frequency Distribution of Pupils’ Learning Outcomes*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	41	21%
Very Satisfactory	57	28%
Satisfactory	66	33%
Fairly Satisfactory	36	18%
Did not meet Expectation	0	0
Total	200	100%

It can be asserted that out of 200 respondents 66 (33%) were rated Satisfactory (80-85%) while only 36 or 18% were rated Fairly Satisfactory. It can be asserted that more pupils achieved reasonable academic performance. This means that teachers’ professional development program has contributed to the improvement of pupils’ learning outcomes.

Subsequently, teachers’ professional development program is one of the continuing education efforts for educators. It is one of the strategies to improve teachers’ teaching and pedagogical skills and competence which helps boost learners’ learning outcomes.

Bernal and Wilson (2020) averred that learning takes place in both in formal and informal modalities. Formal professional development program include conferences, courses, seminars, retreats and workshops. Informal learning, in the other hand, provides opportunities for teachers’ professional development include independent research or investigation, peer learning initiatives or even talking online with colleagues, school heads, or master teacher.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of pupils’ learning outcomes and the extent of professional development program in terms of: Teachers’ Knowledge, Teachers’ Practice, and Teachers’ Efficacy?

Table 3. *Statistical Result of the Interplay Between the Professional Development Program and Pupils’ Learning Outcomes*

<i>Teachers’ Professional Development Program</i>			<i>Pupils’ Learning Outcomes</i>	
	<i>(r)</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>H01</i>
Teaches’ Knowledge	.116	.626	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted
Teachers’ Practice	.123	.606	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted
Teachers’ Efficacy	.065	.785	Denotes Negligible Correlation	Accepted

Table 3 presents the interplay between the level of pupils’ learning outcomes and the extent of teachers’ professional development programs in terms of teachers’ knowledge, teachers’ practice, and teachers’ efficacy. The table depicts that teachers’ knowledge denotes negligible correlation to pupils’ learning outcomes as evident by the computed r value of .116 which is lower than the significant value of .626. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued logically, that pupils’ learning outcomes was not correlated with teaches’ professional development program in terms of teachers’ knowledge.

Subsequently, teachers’ professional development program in terms of teachers’ practice denotes negligible correlation to pupils’ learning outcomes as evident by the computed r value of .123 which is lower than the significant value of .606. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be deduced based on findings that pupils’ learning outcomes was not influenced by teachers’ professional development program in terms of teachers’ practice.

Consequently, teachers’ professional development program in terms of teachers’ efficacy denotes negligible correlation to pupils’ learning outcomes as evident by the computed r value of .065 which is lower than the significant value of .785. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be exemplified based on findings that teachers’ efficacy in teaching did not stimulate pupils’ learning outcomes.

In summary, teachers’ knowledge, teachers’ practice, and teachers’ efficacy do not predict pupils’ learning outcomes. These findings

were incongruence to the findings of Bernal and Wilson (2020) who revealed that teachers' professional development program in terms of teachers' knowledge, teachers' practice, and teachers' efficacy influenced pupils' learning outcomes.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Teachers' professional development program is a continuous and year-round development of the teaching personnel of the Department of Education implemented with the purpose of improving teachers' teaching competence and effectiveness to sustain quality of teaching which benefit the public school pupils. It is during the training program that the teachers will be able to learn and relearn different functional teaching strategies and techniques, classroom management, handling pupils with different special learning needs and development issues, and learn different technologies used in teaching to sustain the type of education in the version of the Department of Education.

Pupils' learning outcomes is the influence of different personal, psychological, and environment factors such as pupils' psychological and cognitive maturity of the learners and the learners' immediate environment such as teachers' support and peer group's camaraderie or pressure. However, teachers' knowledge, practice, and efficacy are factors that do not significantly influence pupils' learning outcomes.

Teachers' continuous professional development programs which are scientifically aimed at improving teachers' teaching knowledge, practice, and efficacy do not influence pupils' learning outcomes because there are other factors that significantly influence pupils' learning such as teachers' personal attributes and pupils' cognitive readiness and maturity.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will be encouraged to design and craft a comprehensive approach to professional development program that is inclusive to the specific learning needs of public school learners.

School Principals/School Heads will be inspired to design and developed a comprehensive approach to teachers' professional development program that is inclusive to the specific learning needs of public school learners.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to continuously take the opportunities for their personal and professional development through trainings, conferences, and seminar-workshops in order to leverage their personal and professional teaching competence.

Parents will be able to provide support in the learning activities designed by teachers to improve their child's academic and learning outcomes. Parental support is indispensable in the academic success of their children, thus, the need to always encourage them to participate and collaborate with teachers in providing necessary learning support.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders will be able to provide more support to school activities especially in improving the pupils' learning outcomes.

Future Researchers will be encouraged to conduct a similar study on the efficiency and effectiveness of teaching to help improve pupils' learning outcomes as well as to identify the need of developing an intervention material to promote pupils' collaboration and engagements in the performance tasks to develop positive learning outcomes.

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